

SMRs Core Design Calculations Using Monte Carlo And Simplified Thermal-Hydraulic Approach

Dušan Čalič¹, Klemen Ambrožič^{1,2}

¹Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

² Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

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ABSTRACT

A modular multiphysics framework was developed and tested on a NuScale-like small modular reactor (SMR) core, focusing on critical boron concentration calculations across the operating cycle. The system couples continuous-energy Monte Carlo neutron transport in Serpent 2 with a simplified assembly-wise thermal-hydraulic solver, derived from the CTEMP module of the CORD-2 system, to capture reactivity feedback from fuel temperature and coolant density under Hot Zero Power (HZIP), Hot Full Power (HFP) and burnup (BRN) conditions. In this work, the framework is exercised for HFP and BRN conditions to predict the critical boron concentration (boron letdown curve) of a NuScale-like core. Full-core simulations demonstrate predictive capability for core design analyses, indicating that the approach is suitable for detailed SMR core-design studies. The present study represents a preliminary implementation in which adaptive underrelaxation is applied only to the soluble-boron iteration, while extensions to relaxed thermal-hydraulic fields and a more detailed stability assessment proposed for future work.

Keywords: multiphysics, SMRs, core design, Monte Carlo

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern nuclear reactor analysis increasingly relies on multiphysics tools that couple neutronics, thermal-hydraulics and fuel performance within high-fidelity simulations. Recent international initiatives [1–3] have led to the development of integrated environments such as VERA [4] and the MOOSE framework [5], which link Monte Carlo or advanced deterministic transport solvers with detailed TH and fuel-performance models.

Within this context, the Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI) has long-standing experience in full-core reactor simulations, most notably through the in-house non-commercial CORD-2 system [6], which has been successfully applied to Krško NPP core-design analyses for more than three decades. Building on this foundation, JSI has developed a new modular simulator extending its core-analysis capabilities to small modular reactor (SMR) design.

The framework couples continuous-energy Monte Carlo transport in Serpent 2 [7] with a streamlined thermal-hydraulic feedback loop implemented in external Fortran modules, automates soluble-boron concentration control through Serpent's critical-density iteration, and exchanges power and temperature data via the multiphysics ifc interface. This reduced-order approach preserves the geometric fidelity of explicit Monte Carlo core modelling at the fuel-assembly level while remaining significantly cheaper than detailed subchannel or CFD-based couplings. The main contribution of this work is the construction of this Serpent-driven multiphysics framework, combining an assembly-wise

CTEMP-based thermal-hydraulic model with an automated boron-control loop to enable practical full-core SMR critical-boron and burnup analysis.

Since in PWR-type LWRs the soluble-boron concentration provides the dominant reactivity control over the operating cycle, the present work focuses primary on a robust treatment of this effect. The implementation presented here employs adaptive underrelaxation only for the scalar soluble-boron concentration, while assembly-wise thermal-hydraulic feedback fields are currently updated without additional relaxation. A more systematic numerical-stability analysis, including possible underrelaxation strategies for the thermal-hydraulic fields, is planned to future work. The following sections summarize the methodology, describe the computational model, and present results for a NuScale-like SMR case.

2. METHODOLOGY

The simulation framework models the SMR core through an integrated feedback loop coupling Monte Carlo neutron transport with thermal-hydraulic behaviour. Neutronic calculations are performed using Serpent 2, while the thermal response is handled by auxiliary Fortran modules built around the CTEMP subroutine. CTEMP is a validated fuel-temperature solver originating from the CORD-2 reactor-physics system, which has been applied in Krško NPP analyses over more than 35 fuel cycles [8]. In the present work, CTEMP is used to compute UO_2 fuel temperature and density feedback, forming the core of the thermal-hydraulic feedback model. The following subsections briefly describe the main physical models.

2.1. Neutron Transport

Neutron transport and depletion are solved in explicit three-dimensional geometry using Serpent 2 [7]. The simulator supports both full-core and one-eighth-core symmetric configurations, combining spatial fidelity with computational efficiency. During burnup steps, Serpent's internal depletion solver updates nuclide compositions using restart files, while temperature-dependent cross sections are updated through ifc files reflecting the current thermal state. Gd_2O_3 pins are subdivided radially into ten concentric annuli to resolve self-shielding effects, whereas UO_2 pins remain homogeneous.

2.2. Boron control

Under hot full power (HFP) and burnup (BRN) conditions, the reactor is maintained near criticality by dynamically adjusting the soluble-boron concentration in the moderator. The critical boron concentration is determined through a coupled iterative procedure combining Serpent's internal iteration capability with an external post-processing script.

During each iteration, Serpent's 'set iter' routine rescales the atomic densities of ^{10}B and ^{11}B to achieve a critical solution ($k_{\text{eff}} \approx 1.00$). Serpent then outputs the parameter *ITER_FACTOR*, which represents the ratio between the target and the achieved effective multiplication factor, and defines a raw boron update $B_{\text{raw}}(k+1) = B(k) \times \text{ITER_FACTOR}$. The external program UpdateBoron treats this as a trial value and applies an adaptive underrelaxation:

$$B(k+1) = (1 - \alpha)B(k) + \alpha B_{\text{raw}}(k+1) \quad (1)$$

where $B(k)$ is the boron concentration used in iteration k , $B_{raw}(k+1)$ is the value implied by $ITER_FACTOR$, and α is an adaptive relaxation factor (termed damping in the code) that is reduced as the raw correction $|B_{raw}(k+1) - B(k)|$ becomes small, in order to prevent overshoot and oscillatory behaviour near the critical solution. At low boron levels the maximum change per-iteration is limited further and negative boron values are explicitly prevented. Convergence is reached when $|B(k+1) - B(k)| < \text{tolerance}$ (typically 2–3 ppm). Each iteration updates the boron state file, logs the iteration history, and, upon convergence, records the final boron value for the current burnup step.

This automated mechanism provides self-consistent control of soluble-boron concentration without manual tuning, mirroring the operational approach of pressurized-water reactors (PWRs). In the NuScale-like cases considered here, the boron update scheme was applied independently at each burnup step of the Hot Full Power (HFP) all-rods-out (ARO) simulations, yielding the critical-boron values reported in Table I.

2.3. Thermal-Hydraulic calculations

Thermal hydraulic feedback is implemented through Serpent's multiphysics interface (ifc). The interface exchanges assembly-wise power distributions from Serpent and temperature - density fields computed by the auxiliary solver, enabling iterative coupling between the neutronic and thermal hydraulic domains.

Power tallies exported by Serpent are post-processed and, after optional smoothing of the axial shapes, rescaled so that the sum over all assemblies and axial regions exactly equals the prescribed core thermal power P_{core} . This rescaling affects only the post-processed tallies used as input to the thermal-hydraulic solver and is fully consistent with the fixed power specified in the Serpent calculation; the burnup and xenon evolution are still governed by the power defined in the Serpent input. After this normalization, the assembly-wise axial profiles are preserved by applying a local renormalization inside each assembly so that the relative axial shapes are maintained.

The normalized regional powers are then converted to linear heat generation rates using the number of pins and the height of each axial region, which are the quantities provided to the thermal model. The model combines two complementary solvers. The first reconstructs the pellet, gap, cladding and coolant geometry for each axial region and evaluates the enthalpy rise, coolant mixing and flow conditions. Within every region, it computes the mixed coolant temperature, defined here as the mass-flow-weighted average coolant temperature over the assembly flow cross section in each axial region, and the corresponding density, using one-dimensional correlations for heat transfer and pressure drop, and tabulated water and steam properties based on thermodynamic properties of water [9].

The second solver refines these results by applying burnup- and power-dependent temperature increments for the fuel and cladding. It relies on pre-calculated tables that give the temperature rise of the fuel and cladding as functions of burnup and linear heat rate (W cm^{-1}). For each region, the routine performs a two-stage interpolation, first across the burnup grid (BU) and then across the power anchor points (P_{in}), to obtain the temperature increments $\Delta T_{fuel}(BU, P_{in})$ and $\Delta T_{clad}(BU, P_{in})$. These are added to the mixed coolant temperature from the first solver to obtain self-consistent material temperatures:

$$T_{fuel} = T_{mix} + \Delta T_{fuel}(BU, P_{in}), \quad T_{clad} = T_{mix} + \Delta T_{clad}(BU, P_{in}) \quad (2)$$

This approach captures both the instantaneous thermal response to power and the gradual burnup-induced evolution of fuel and cladding temperature. It provides physically realistic temperature

distributions while avoiding the additional cost and complexity of detailed pin-wise radial conduction and subchannel-level modelling in the coupled Monte Carlo–TH scheme.

The resulting fuel, gap, cladding and moderator temperatures, together with the updated coolant densities, are written back into the assembly data structures and passed to Serpent via ifc files for the next neutronic iteration. The inner loop continues until both reactivity and thermal fields satisfy user-defined tolerances, with conservation of total power enforced at each step so that the sum of regional powers matches the target core thermal power while preserving per-assembly axial distributions. The outer boron-iteration loop is controlled by the UpdateBoron driver described in Section 2.1.2, which applies adaptive underrelaxation and a tight ppm-level convergence criterion to the soluble-boron concentration. For the NuScale-like test cases analysed in this work, the coupled neutronic–thermal–hydraulic–boron scheme converged for all burnup points, and no oscillatory behaviour was observed in the critical boron or k_{eff} histories.

3. CALCULATIONAL MODEL

The simulation workflow was tested by analysing the core of the NuScale small modular reactor (SMR). The model follows the numerical code-to-code benchmark defined in [10], with additional implementation details, verification for operational conditions and schematic views of the core layout given in [11]. Only the main features relevant to the present work are summarized here.

3.1. Model geometry

The core is modelled using one-eighth symmetry and consists of UO_2 fuel assemblies with an active fuel height of 200 cm and six ^{235}U enrichments (1.5, 1.6, 2.5, 2.6, 4.05 and 4.55 wt.%). Four assemblies contain 16 Gd_2O_3 -bearing fuel rods each, with a gadolinium concentration of 8 wt.% Gd_2O_3 . The core is surrounded by a heavy-steel reflector and enclosed within a cylindrical core barrel; remaining geometric and material details follow the benchmark specification [10].

Spacer grids are represented as additional regions inside the fuel-rod and guide-tube cells of the fuel-assembly lattice. In contrast to the square regions used in [10], they are here modelled as cylindrical zones of equivalent volume within the fuel-pin definitions, while axial locations and material compositions are kept unchanged. Axially, the model extends from the bottom of the lower nozzle (0 cm) to the top of the upper nozzle (243.56 cm), with the active fuel region spanning 11.356–211.365 cm (200 cm total).

3.2. Model materials

All non-fuel and non-cooling materials follow the definitions given in [10]. Fuel-assembly characteristics are specified in a dedicated input library providing the assembly ID, uranium enrichment, uranium mass, $\text{Gd}_2\text{O}_3/\text{UO}_2$ mass ratio, burnup, and assembly type.

The coolant is light water (H_2O), whose density and boron concentration depend on temperature and pressure. While temperature is determined by the procedure described in Section 2.2, density (ρ) is calculated using tabulated data [9] with interpolation. The routine first validates that input values lie within the table range (0–350 °C, 120–180 bar), identifies the bracketing temperature and pressure nodes, and interpolates the specific volume (v): quadratically in temperature within the liquid region, with a

linear fallback near the two-phase boundary. It then linearly interpolates the pressure and converts specific volume to density ($\rho = 1/v$).

3.3. Fuel and burnable absorber configuration

A single gadolinium-bearing fuel configuration was analysed, consistent with the NuScale-like benchmark defined in [10]. Four fuel assemblies contain 16 gadolinium-bearing fuel rods each, with a gadolinium concentration of 8 wt% Gd_2O_3 in the burnable-absorber pins. All other model characteristics, including core geometry, enrichment zoning, reflector composition, coolant properties, and thermal-hydraulic feedback treatment, follow the setup described in Sections 3.1–3.2.

The $UO_2 + Gd_2O_3$ assemblies use the same lattice and structural definitions as the standard UO_2 assemblies, differing only in the number and spatial arrangement of absorber pins within the lattice.

3.4. Operating conditions

The simulator employs a state-driven mechanism for setting operating conditions and organizing output. At the start of each run, the thermal state (HZP, HFP, BRN) and xenon conditions are selected. For HZP, all characteristic temperatures (moderator, fuel, cladding, gap) are initialized to a uniform coolant temperature of 558 K, representing the nominal hot zero-power condition. For HFP and BRN, the coolant inlet temperature is set to 531 K, consistent with the nominal full-power inlet temperature, and the outlet temperature is obtained from the thermal-hydraulic model. The main plant parameters are: core thermal power 160 MW, average primary pressure 127.55 bar and total coolant mass flow 587 $kg\ s^{-1}$.

At HZP conditions, the simulator normalizes the thermal power to 15% of core value, otherwise full power normalization is used. These settings are automatically propagated to the Serpent input (e.g., *set power*), ensuring consistent neutron-transport normalization, temperature initialization, and subsequent thermal routines.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

The results in this section summarize the performance of the developed simulation framework applied to the NuScale-like reactor core under hot full power (HFP) and all rods out (ARO) conditions. The analysis verifies the stability, accuracy, and consistency of the coupled neutronic and thermal-hydraulic methodology. The focus is placed on determining the critical boron concentration during burnup and characterizing the reactivity behaviour of the Gd_2O_3 bearing core.

All calculations were performed using fuel assemblies discretized into six axial regions with relative heights 1–2–4–4–2–1. A neutron population of 100,000 neutrons per cycle was employed ("*set pop*" 100000 100 50), with 50 inactive cycles for source convergence and 100 active cycles for statistical sampling. In addition, the boron iteration was carried out with "*set iter nuc*" 50 1.000 2 50100 50110, which introduces a further 50 non-active cycles while the boron concentration is adjusted. In total, therefore, 100 cycles are discarded before tallying, while about 15 million neutron histories are accumulated per state.

With these settings, the typical statistical uncertainty in the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} remained below ± 20 pcm. Serpent's built-in convergence diagnostics, namely the Shannon entropy of the fission

source (*HIS_ENTR_SPT*) and the cycle-wise k_{eff} histories (*HIS_IMP_KEFF*, *HIS_ANA_KEFF*), show a clear plateau within the first 20–30 cycles, well before the start of the active cycles, indicating that the fission source is well converged and that variance underestimation is not expected to be significant for the reported results.

At the fuel-assembly level, power tallies for all eight assemblies were well converged, with relative 1- σ errors ranging from approximately 0.09 % to 0.31 % (median \sim 0.14 %) at middle of cycle (360 days). Assembly-level rotational symmetries were exploited using Serpent's "*set usym*" option: for the UO_2 fuel assemblies, the 1/8 rotational symmetry of the pin layout allowed us to model only a 45° sector, corresponding to 39 explicitly simulated fuel rods per assembly, whereas the Gd_2O_3 fuel assembly, containing 16 gadolinium-bearing rods, exhibits only 1/4 symmetry and was therefore modelled using a 90° sector containing 72 rods. With seven UO_2 assemblies and one Gd_2O_3 assembly, the model included a total of 345 fuel rods. For individual rod (pin) powers, 295 of the 345 pins (85.5 %) exhibited relative errors below 1 %, and all remained below 2 %.

The critical-boron concentration was obtained using the iterative procedure described in Section 2.1.2, ensuring physical consistency under full-power and burnup conditions. All simulations employed Serpent 2.2.0 with the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library [12]. For the boron iteration, 50 additional inactive cycles were executed to guarantee convergence, and 1,390 nuclides were included in the burnup calculations. The ARO configuration was used throughout.

4.1. Critical Boron Concentration at HFP and ARO Conditions During Burnup

Table I presents the calculated critical boron concentrations for hot full power (HFP) conditions with all control rods withdrawn (ARO). Because exact numerical values and detailed core conditions for the NuScale equilibrium cycle are not publicly available, a comparison curve was reconstructed from Figure 4.3-17 of the NuScale Design Certification Application [13], which shows the equilibrium-cycle boron behaviour. Values were extracted directly from the published figure, introducing an estimated uncertainty of about ± 15 ppm due to digitization and graphical-resolution limits. In addition, the underlying design assumptions in [13] (e.g. exact gadolinium loading and fuel-management details) are not fully specified, so the reconstructed curve should be regarded as an indicative reference for trend and magnitude rather than a strict benchmark dataset.

The results for the configuration defined in Section 3.3, with 16 gadolinium pins per Gd_2O_3 assembly, show the expected decrease in boron concentration with increasing burnup. At the beginning of life, the presence of gadolinium leads to a relatively high initial boron concentration (1261 ppm in the simulation versus a reconstructed reference value of 1235 ppm), reflecting the combined effect of burnable absorbers and soluble boron control. As burnup proceeds and gadolinium isotopes progressively deplete, the boron-letdown curve becomes increasingly governed by fuel-isotopic evolution and fission-product accumulation. Over the range from 0 to 12 000 MWd/kgU, the simulated critical boron concentrations remain within an average absolute difference of approximately 51 ppm and a maximum deviation of 113 ppm at 1000 MWd/kgU. End of the cycle is defined as the point at which the soluble boron concentration approaches about 20 ppm or less [13], so this final point should be viewed as a burnup state beyond the nominal end of cycle rather than a direct end-of-cycle comparison.

Table I. Critical boron concentration at HFP and ARO conditions with equilibrium xenon at different burnup steps, with no xenon conditions at zero burnup step(*).

Burnup (MWd/kgU)	Ref (ppm)	Simulation (ppm)
0	1235	1261*
1000	1105	992
2000	1007	911
3000	905	836
4000	803	751
5000	696	670
6000	592	580
7000	491	495
8000	391	411
9000	293	330
10000	194	246
11000	101	168
12000	0	91

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a preliminary modular simulation framework for small modular reactor (SMR) cores, with emphasis on a NuScale-like pressurized water reactor. The framework integrates Monte Carlo neutronics with thermal-hydraulic feedback and automated boron iteration control, providing a flexible platform for full-core multiphysics analysis.

The methodology was applied to the NuScale-like benchmark core using the Serpent 2 code and the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library. A configuration with 16 gadolinium-bearing fuel pins per Gd_2O_3 assembly, consistent with the benchmark, was investigated to study the impact of burnable-absorber loading on the critical boron concentration during burnup. The results showed good consistency with the reconstructed boron-letdown curve, exhibiting the expected trend of decreasing soluble boron concentration with increasing burnup. At early burnup, the presence of gadolinium leads to a relatively high initial boron concentration, while at higher burnup the behaviour is governed mainly by fuel-isotopic evolution and fission-product buildup.

All simulations achieved statistical convergence with effective multiplication-factor uncertainties below ± 20 pcm, indicating that the Monte Carlo results are well resolved for the cases considered. The framework also demonstrated practical computational performance on a modern compute node, with runtimes remaining feasible for design and analysis work at the neutron populations used in this study. The combined effect of the *ITER_FACTOR* statistical uncertainty ($\approx \pm 2$ ppm in boron) and the 2–3 ppm convergence tolerance corresponds to a numerical uncertainty in the critical-boron concentration of at most about 5 ppm, which is negligible compared to the uncertainties associated with the reconstructed boron-letdown curve and core-modelling assumptions. These results suggest that the approach is computationally practical for high-resolution SMR analyses with iterative boron control and multiphysics feedback.

Future work will extend the framework to multi-cycle burnup with control-rod modelling and an improved treatment of thermal-hydraulic feedback, and will validate the methodology against core-follow data from the Krško NPP to assess its predictive accuracy under realistic operating conditions.

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